

Adult-Onset Tuberous Sclerosis Complex Presenting as Chronic Lumbar Pain: A Case Report of Symptomatic Renal Angiomyolipoma

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Abstract

Tuberous sclerosis complex (TSC) is a rare autosomal dominant neurocutaneous disorder characterized by hamartomas in multiple organs, including the brain, kidneys, liver, and lungs. Neurological manifestations, such as epilepsy, typically lead to diagnosis in childhood. This case report describes an atypical presentation in adulthood, with chronic lumbar pain as the primary symptom prompting diagnosis of symptomatic renal

angiomyolipoma, illustrating diagnostic challenges and management limitations in resource-limited settings. A 28-year-old woman with a history of childhood epilepsy and family history of epilepsy presented with persistent chronic lower back pain refractory to analgesics. She had no cutaneous stigmata or neurological deficits. Investigations revealed bilateral renal angiomyolipomas (AMLs), hepatic cysts, pulmonary cystic changes, and cerebral cortical tubers with subependymal nodules on MRI/CT. A large left renal AML of epithelioid variant prompted nephrectomy due to mass effect and suspected malignant transformation. Histopathology confirmed epithelioid AML. This case illustrates the phenotypic variability of TSC and the potential for delayed diagnosis when renal manifestations predominate in adulthood. It underscores the need for lifelong multisystem surveillance and timely use of mTOR inhibitors to avoid invasive procedures, particularly where access is limited.

Introduction

Tuberous sclerosis complex (TSC) is an autosomal dominant neurocutaneous disorder caused by pathogenic variants in TSC1 or TSC2 genes, leading to constitutive activation of the mTOR pathway. It is characterized by hamartomas in multiple organs, predominantly the brain, kidneys, skin, heart, and lungs [1,2]. TSC is generally recognized as a childhood-onset disease, with neurological manifestations such as infantile spasms, epilepsy, and developmental delay often constituting its initial presentation [1,3-5]. Renal involvement, mainly through renal AMLs, is highly prevalent and affects up to 80% of adult patients. It is the leading cause of mortality in this age group due to the risk of hemorrhage or chronic kidney disease [3]. While the diagnosis of TSC relies on established clinical and radiological criteria, delayed diagnosis in adulthood remains a significant challenge, particularly when the primary symptoms are non-neurological. This case is noteworthy for its atypical presentation with chronic lumbar pain as the diagnostic trigger in a patient without classic cutaneous features, emphasizing diagnostic difficulties in settings with limited genetic testing and the value of comprehensive surveillance.

Materials and Methods

We report the case of a 28-year-old single female patient, born from a non-consanguineous marriage, with a family history of epilepsy in her father and sibling (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Pedigree of the Patient’s Family

Her clinical history was marked by childhood-onset epilepsy, for which antiepileptic treatment was

initiated in another hospital. Renal function was also preserved. In adulthood, the patient developed persistent chronic lower back pain. The Lumbar pain, which was refractory to standard analgesic treatment, was the sole presenting complaint that prompted a comprehensive investigation, leading to the definitive diagnosis of TSC.

Clinical and Radiological Investigations

On physical examination, the patient exhibited no evident neurological deficit. Additionally, a detailed dermatological assessment revealed no typical cutaneous stigmata of TSC, such as facial angiofibromas or shagreen patches.

Results

Renal Findings

Initial abdominal ultrasonography revealed multiple hyperechoic nodules and small bilateral cysts suggestive of angiomyolipomas. Subsequent thoracoabdominal CT-Scan (Figure 2) confirmed multiple cortical masses in the left kidney, consistent with angiomyolipomas. Given the size and persistence of the refractory lumbar pain, left nephrectomy was performed due to the significant mass effect.

Figure 2. Thoracoabdominal-Pelvic Computed Tomography (CT) Scan, Axial View, Showing Multiple Low-Density Cortical Angiomyolipomas (AMLs) in the Left Kidney (red arrows) in a Patient with TSC

Histopathological examination of the surgical specimen confirmed the presence of an angiomyolipoma of the

epithelioid variant, suggesting a potential malignant transformation.

Cerebral Findings

Brain MRI (Figure 3), performed as part of the systemic evaluation, confirmed the typical cerebral lesions of TSC, including multiple subependymal nodules (SENs) and cortical tubers. There was no evidence of obstructing subependymal giant cell astrocytoma (SEGA).

Figure 3. Brain MRI (Axial T2- FLAIR sequence) Showing Multiple Characteristic Hyperintense Cortical Tubers (arrows) Consistent with Tuberous Sclerosis Complex (TSC)

Other systemic Findings

The thoracoabdominal CT-scan also revealed multiple hepatic nodules and complex cystic pulmonary changes. Echocardiography was unremarkable and ruled out cardiac involvement.

Discussion

This case report describes a rare presentation of tuberous sclerosis complex in a 28-year-old woman, highlighting the challenges of delayed diagnosis and the potential severity of systemic complications in adulthood. The definitive diagnosis of TSC was established only after investigation of chronic, debilitating lumbar pain, which was ultimately attributed to symptomatic renal angiomyolipoma.

TSC is typically diagnosed during childhood because of common early manifestations, such as epilepsy and characteristic cutaneous stigmata [1,2]. Although childhood epilepsy, reported in 80%-90% of patients and often beginning as infantile spasms [4,5], was present in our patient, it did not lead to an early diagnosis. Early onset seizures are also associated with an increased risk of developmental delays and autism spectrum disorders [6,7]. While the management of TSC-associated epilepsy follows established international recommendations, the lack of

recognizable cutaneous lesions in our patient likely contributed to the delayed diagnosis.

The onset of significant renal symptoms as the first major diagnostic clue during the third decade of life is an unusual occurrence [2]. This presentation underscores the need for physicians to consider TSC in the differential diagnosis of adult patients presenting with unexplained multiorgan hamartomatous lesions, even in the absence of obvious pediatric or cutaneous features of TSC. This consideration is particularly relevant in settings where access to extensive genetic screening or specialized pediatric neurology follow-up is limited. In this case, the diagnosis relied primarily on radiological criteria, including the identification of cortical tubers and subependymal nodules on Brain MRI (Figure 3), along with visceral findings. The high phenotypic variability in TSC can be explained by differences between *TSC1* and *TSC2* mutations and mosaicism. Although genetic analysis was not performed in our case, this coexistence of severe renal disease and a family history of epilepsy (consistent with potential familial TSC) warrants comprehensive genetic counseling.

Renal Angiomyolipomas (AMLs) are the most frequent renal manifestations of TSC, affecting up to 80% of adult patients, and are the primary cause of disease-related mortality in this age group due to the risk of hemorrhage or chronic kidney disease [3]. The chronic lumbar pain experienced by our patient was directly attributable to a large AMLs, demonstrating the high morbidity associated with these lesions. Furthermore, while cardiac findings of rhabdomyomas are typically seen in the neonatal period, our patient's unremarkable echocardiography illustrates the clinical heterogeneity of TSC [2,8].

Crucially, the histopathological finding of angiomyolipoma with an epithelioid variant carries specific prognostic weight. Although AMLs are generally benign, the epithelioid subtype is a recognized distinct entity that requires careful scrutiny because of its potential for malignant behavior [9,10]. This finding justifies the need for urgent invasive intervention (nephrectomy), resulting in the loss of functional renal parenchyma and emphasizing the severe consequences of a delayed diagnosis that precludes early medical management.

The management of TSC-associated AMLs has advanced with the introduction of mTOR inhibitors (e.g., Everolimus). These agents have demonstrated efficacy in reducing AML volume and preventing complications, often avoiding the need for invasive procedures such as embolization or nephrectomy [11,12]. Furthermore, these inhibitors are the standard treatment for growing Subependymal Giant Cell Astrocytomas (SEGAs). While the benefits of mTOR inhibitors are well documented, the immediate

necessity of nephrectomy due to the large, symptomatic nature and potential malignancy of the lesion in our patient highlights the ongoing challenge of accessing and implementing preemptive mTOR inhibitor therapy in certain contexts. A multidisciplinary evaluation is needed to weight surgical risks against the long-term benefits of targeted medical therapy.

Therefore, our case strongly advocates for prolonged, life-long systemic surveillance in all patients with a confirmed diagnosis of TSC. A comprehensive evaluation, including Brain MRI (Figure 3), abdominal CT/MRI (Figure 2), and echocardiography, is non-negotiable. The multisystemic nature of the disease requires a dedicated multidisciplinary approach involving neurologists, nephrologists, and geneticists to manage the evolving complications [2]. This observation reinforces the importance of regular follow-up to detect and manage lesions, such as AMLs, before they become symptomatic and require aggressive surgical intervention.

Conclusion

This case of Tuberous Sclerosis Complex presenting with chronic lumbar pain due to symptomatic renal angiomyolipoma highlights an uncommon diagnostic challenge in adult medicine. This reinforces the need for a high index of clinical suspicion for TSC in the setting of unexplained multi-organ hamartomas, regardless of patient age. Furthermore, this observation underscores the critical importance of regular, comprehensive systemic surveillance and timely consideration of mTOR inhibitors to preserve renal function and prevent aggressive or invasive complications.

Ethical Considerations

Formal approval from an institutional ethics committee was not required for this single observational case report in accordance with local regulations. The study was conducted in compliance with the Declaration of Helsinki. Written informed consent for publication was obtained from the patient.

Conflict of Interests

Authors declare no conflict of interest.

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